

Obesity Epidemiology in Nigeria: Overview

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Abstract

Obesity is a manageable and preventable problem, but it affects 39 percent of the global population. Obesity and overweight are associated with a higher death rate worldwide, according to research. Nigeria's fast rising healthcare expenses are attributed to high obesity rates. Despite the serious nature of obesity's contribution to Nigeria's poor health outcomes, it is surprising that little is being done at the national level to address the issue. As a result, the purpose of this study is to describe the epidemiology of obesity, investigate the causes of obesity in Nigeria, and provide a solution. Reports and research briefs from World Health Organization, Obesity Society, Population Bureau, World Obesity, Centre for Disease Control and Prevention was used for this review. In addition literature searches from peer-reviewed articles available in databases such as Google Scholar were also employed for this work. In order to provide Nigerians with a holistic approach to combating food and nutrition insecurity, the Nigerian government revised its National Food and Nutrition Policy in 2016. The Finance Act of 2021 includes an excise levy of N10 per liter imposed by the Federal Government on non-alcoholic, carbonated, and sugar-sweetened beverages. Although a sugar tax may not be the solution to a poor eating pattern, it is predicted to stimulate a reduction in sugar-sweetened beverage consumption, hence addressing diet-related noncommunicable diseases.

Keywords: Obesity, Epidemic, Overweight, Nigeria

Introduction

Obesity is a manageable and preventable problem, but it affects 39 percent of the global population (1,2). Obesity and overweight are associated with more fatalities worldwide, as the risk of noncommunicable illnesses increases with body mass index (3). Body mass index (BMI) is a measurement of body fat based on height and weight that applies to both adult men and women (3). According to research, obesity-related illnesses such as cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes, and hypertension are among the major causes of death (4). Furthermore, overweight and obesity-related comorbidities cause approximately 2.8 million deaths worldwide and an estimated 35.8 million disability adjusted life years (DALYs) (3, 5, 6).

According to a study (7), the prevalence of obesity is higher in women than males, and most countries of the world have observed this tendency, particularly among women (8-12). Women are more prone to

noncommunicable diseases such as hypertension and type 2 diabetes due to their higher obesity rate (13).

Furthermore, poor eating habits and a negative opinion of body weight can increase an individual's risk of obesity. Furthermore, low-income earners are more prone to obesity-related comorbidities because they lack the resources to purchase fruits and vegetables and prefer to spend less money on unhealthy foods (14). On the other hand, (10) said that educational achievement has a considerable impact on weight control, implying that university graduates are less likely to be obese than individuals with lesser educational attainment. Similarly, a number of studies have demonstrated that the prevalence of obesity varies with educational level and income, albeit trends may change between rich and low-income nations (10,12).

Factors impacting healthy eating and active living among individuals and households include physical activity norms, dietary patterns, insufficient information about the health benefits of these activities, a lack of cooking abilities, and participation in physical activity (15). Furthermore, physical activity is one of the best strategies to prevent heart disease, mental illness, and improve physical fitness (15). This is because it reduces the risk factors associated with a variety of diseases, such as diabetes, hypertension, and obesity.

The risk of being overweight or obese can be reduced by consuming less calories from fats and sweets and more calories from fruits, vegetables, legumes, whole grains, and nuts (13). This risk can also be reduced by engaging in regular physical activity, which should last 60 minutes for children and 150 minutes for adults. Despite dispute about the appropriate timing of physical activity for weight management, the hours of 7 a.m. to 9 a.m. appear to be the best time of day to increase the connection between daily moderate to vigorous physical exercise and obesity (16).

Furthermore, Nigeria's fast rising healthcare expenses are driven by high obesity rates (17). Despite the serious nature of obesity's contribution to Nigeria's poor health outcomes, it is surprising that little is being done at the national level to address the issue. The current study intends to investigate the epidemiology of Nigeria's illness burden using this premise.

Objectives of the Paper

- 1) Discuss the epidemiology of obesity
- 2) Examine the drivers of obesity in Nigeria
- 3) Present the way forward

Methods:

This review was based on reports and research briefs from the World Health Organization, Obesity Society, Population Bureau, World Obesity, and the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. In addition, literature searches from peer-reviewed articles available in databases such as Google Scholar were conducted for this paper.

Inclusion criteria: Studies were selected based on the use of body mass index (BMI) to define obesity. We considered original publications on population-based studies conducted in adults, children, and adolescents that reported independent prevalence of overweight and obesity.

Exclusion criteria: Publications including self-reports of overweight and obesity.

Epidemiologic Assessment of Obesity in Nigeria

Overweight and obesity are terms used to describe any abnormal or excessive fat accumulation that poses a health risk (3,18). Obesity is a complex condition marked by excessive fat buildup and health hazards. A body mass index (BMI) greater than 25 is considered overweight; a BMI greater than 30 is termed obese. According to research, higher-than-optimal BMI caused five million deaths from noncommunicable diseases (NCDs) in 2019 (3). About 2.5 billion persons over the age of 18 were overweight in 2022, with more than 890 million obese. This indicates that 43 percent of adults aged 18 and up—43% males and 44% women—were overweight. This represents an increase from 25% of adults in this age range in 1990. In 2022, 16% of persons globally aged 18 and over were obese (1,3).

Obesity rates worldwide more than doubled between 1990 and 2022. It is anticipated that 37 million children under the age of five would be overweight by 2022. This disease appears to be increasing as incomes rise (3). Obesity was formerly thought to be a concern in high-income countries, but it is now becoming more prevalent in poor and middle-income countries (3, 19).

Since 2000, the number of overweight children under the age of five in Africa has climbed by more than 23 percent. In 2022, more than 390 million children and adolescents aged 5 to 19 were overweight. The prevalence of overweight (including obesity) among children and adolescents aged 5-19 has increased dramatically, from 8% in 1990 to 20% in 2022 (3). Both boys and girls have experienced an increase in overweight people. In 2022, 21% of males and 19% of females were overweight. In 1990, only 2% of children and adolescents aged 5 to 19 (about 31 million young people) were fat. However, by 2022, 8% of children and adolescents (160 million young people) were obese (1,3).

Obesity prevalence in Nigeria was 6.5% in males, 10.3% in girls, 8.3% in boys, and 9.9% in women in 2019. The survey states that 10.3% of boys and 16.7% of girls are overweight, while 18.2% of women are overweight (20). Furthermore, the economic impact of obesity in Nigeria was \$2.57 billion in 2019. The projected cost of obesity-related diseases is the total medical expenditure. The cost is made up of \$1.89 billion in indirect costs, which include presenteeism, absenteeism, and early mortality, and \$477.83 million in direct expenditures, which comprise medical and non-medical expenses such as treatment and travel (21).

Prenatal Risk Factors

Obesity during pregnancy is often characterized as a mother BMI ≥ 30 at the antenatal booking visit (22, 23).

Maternal obesity is one of the most pressing challenges facing women's health this decade. This is because unfavorable pregnancy outcomes are associated with a long-term risk of cardiometabolic disease for both the mother and the child (24). Furthermore, women of reproductive age have a higher risk of cardiovascular disease, such as hypertension (25,26).

Furthermore, newborn morbidity and death have been associated to obesity risk factors such as type 2 diabetes and hypertension (27). As a result, it is critical to understand the link between bad maternal and child outcomes and the overall burden of cardiovascular risk factors prior to pregnancy. Maternal obesity is linked to an increased risk of hypertensive diseases during pregnancy, including preeclampsia (gestational proteinuric hypertension) (28).

Maternal obesity increases the incidence of spontaneous abortion (for both spontaneous and assisted reproductive technology conceptions) and unexplained stillbirth (intrauterine fetal death) (29). A recent cohort study by (30) indicated that women who were obese or very obese had a greater risk of practically all poor pregnancy outcomes, with the risk of stillbirth quadrupled after gestational week 40.

Furthermore, a study found that obese pregnant women had a higher risk of hypertensive problems and gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) (31). Furthermore, obese women were more likely to give birth to a macrosomic infant (Rodriguez and colleagues in 2024). Obese women face a greater risk of problems during labor and delivery (32). As maternal BMI increases, the rate of successful vaginal delivery gradually falls.

In addition, maternal obesity is linked to an increased incidence of diabetes, both pregestational and gestational diabetes mellitus (33), when compared to normal weight women (BMI = 25 kg/m²). The development of GDM has a number of negative maternal and fetal outcomes. Women with GDM are at a higher risk of hyperglycemia, cesarean birth, and diabetes later in life, with more than half developing diabetes within 20 years after giving birth.

The consequences for the offspring could be far more severe. Pregnancies complicated by GDM had a fourfold increase in perinatal mortality and a threefold rise in macrosomia (34). In addition to being larger, infants born from pregnancies affected by GDM have considerably larger skin folds in all areas of measurement (triceps, subscapular flank, thigh, abdomen), putting them at a higher risk of shoulder dystocia and subsequent birth damage. Furthermore, kids of GDM births are more prone to acquire childhood and adult obesity (for every 1-kg increase in

birth weight), as well as type 2 diabetes mellitus (34,35).

However, there is currently no national-level data in Nigeria on the prevalence of obesity during pregnancy. A few observational studies have documented obesity prevalence rates in local maternity populations, and these are currently the best indicators of maternal obesity prevalence in Nigeria (31-36, 37).

Biological Risk Factors

The attempt to address obesity from a population viewpoint does not diminish the importance of genetic or biologically influenced variables in the problem. Given the high calorie availability and low calorie expenditure through physical activity, the prevalence of obesity in various groups underlines the limitations of biological constraints on energy balance (38). However, in terms of mortality caused by biological risk factors, high blood pressure ranks first globally, accounting for 19% of all fatalities, followed by obesity and overweight, as well as elevated blood glucose (5).

Behavioral Risk Factors

Obesity is primarily caused by poor diet and a lack of physical activity. As a result, efforts to establish techniques for delivering nutritious food to society at all stages of life should be stressed (39). Losing weight might be difficult, but maintaining it over time is even more difficult.

Behavior modification is essential for long-term weight management. The social cognitive theory of behavior change proposed by Albert Bandura is advised for an efficient weight management program (40). This is because the theory is well known for creating nutrition education and physical activity, and it is applicable to understanding physical activity health behaviors as a result of interactions between the individual, environment, and behavior. The theory's constructs include self-efficacy, task planning, coping self-efficacy, goal setting, and result expectancy.

Environmental Risk Factors

The lack of secure locations, such as parks, well-lit streets, and walkways, is a substantial barrier to physical activity (41). At the socio-ecological level, people's decisions and habits surrounding active living and a healthy diet are influenced by their physical and social settings, the organizations where they work and learn, and the larger community. As a result, Nigeria's government and community leaders must create an environment that promotes access to nutritional foods as well as safe places for physical activity.

Drivers of Obesity in Nigeria

Figure 1. Showing drivers of obesity in Nigeria (Adapted from dataphyte.com)

In addition, the recent COVID-19 pandemic has changed the environment. Remote work is on the rise. This has resulted in a sustained energy balance, which has produced weight gain. Living a sedentary lifestyle is arguably one of the most important environmental factors that increases a person's risk of morbidity and mortality.

Educational and Ecological Assessment

Gender norms and culture can predict the likelihood of obesity now and in the future. This is related to the fact that social traditions about physical mobility limit women's options for activity, as seen by the variations in physical activity levels between men and women (42). Furthermore, to help households and individuals achieve and maintain energy balance, society must discourage sedentary behavior and excessive calorie intake. Thus, if weight gain trends reverse and the average population's weight falls, the progress gained in treating the consequences of obesity will be offset by a rise in the number of people in need of treatment.

Nigeria is a diverse cultural society. Culture has acted as a barrier to healthy eating and weight perception. For example, in most Nigerian cultures, weight increase, particularly after childbirth, is regarded as a sign of health.

Drivers of Obesity in Nigeria

The seven elements outlined in the accompanying diagram are the primary causes of obesity in Nigeria. The most common issue is a lack of fruit eating (20). Despite the fact that fruits contain simple sugars, which contribute to obesity, they also offer anti-obesity effects. Fruits are a wonderful option for weight loss because they contain vitamins and minerals. Nigeria's

high obesity rate is due to the country's low fruit consumption. In comparison to the WHO's recommended of 400 grams, per capita fruit consumption is low, at 84.2 grams per day. Low exclusive breastfeeding rates are thought to be the country's second greatest cause of obesity.

Furthermore, just 28.7% of the country's infants were exclusively breastfed (20). Low whole grain consumption is the country's third leading cause of obesity. Whole grains have been shown to have a substantial effect on BMI, body fat percentage, waist circumference, and weight gain. Nigerians consume 28.5g of whole grains per day, while the global average is 48g. Other characteristics revealed include mental health diseases (2.9 percent of the population suffers from depression and 2.7% from anxiety disorders), as well as a low per capita consumption of processed meat (1.7 g/day versus the global average of 58 g/day).

Way Forward

Obesity Prevention Strategy/ Policy implementation

Obesity prevention and management necessitate a diverse strategy since the causes of obesity are numerous (43,44). Obesity treatment and prevention involve both pharmaceutical and non-pharmaceutical approaches. Several trials have demonstrated the efficacy of medicinal therapies for obesity therapy (45,46). However, pharmaceutical therapies only provide short-term benefits and are not cost-effective (46). The public health focus is on using cost-effective interventions, preferably non-pharmaceutical interventions, to satisfy population health requirements (47, 48). To minimize obesity, it would be useful to educate individuals about the significance of regular

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Since social media is the most recent trend, using the media to raise awareness of the dangers of obesity and the need to prevent it has proven to be extremely beneficial for social media users (49,50). In recent years, public health professionals have made extensive use of the internet, particularly social media, television, and other age-appropriate media publicity, to educate the public and urge them to adopt healthy lifestyles.

Obesity can also be prevented by culturally relevant therapies (51, 52). Culturally oriented interventions seek to educate and raise knowledge among individuals about what constitutes a healthy diet and optimal body weight (53-56). Even though culture can be a barrier to good eating and weight perception, psycho-education and psychosocial intervention tailored to the cultural needs of people who have bodyweight perception disorders may be useful (57).

For example, a study by (58) looked into the effectiveness of a culturally adjusted dietary obesity prevention program in Nigeria. The study's findings indicate that adult females in culturally relevant programs who received psychological assistance were able to change their bad eating patterns and adhere to healthier diets. This demonstrates that culturally tailored psychosocial interventions may reduce the incidence of unhealthy eating habits among people from various backgrounds.

Conclusion

With an emphasis on the nutritional condition of women and children, the Nigerian government has put in place a number of policies and frameworks to enhance the country's nutrition outcomes. Furthermore, in order to provide Nigerians with a holistic strategy to

combating food and nutrition insecurity, the government updated its National Policy on Food and Nutrition in 2016. The Finance Act of 2021 includes an excise levy of N10 per liter imposed by the Federal Government on non-alcoholic, carbonated, and sugar-sweetened beverages. Although a sugar tax may not be the solution to poor nutrition, it is predicted to stimulate a reduction in sugar-sweetened beverage consumption, hence addressing diet-related noncommunicable diseases.

References

1. World Health Organization. Obesity rising in Africa, WHO analysis finds. 2022. [Accessed on 2024, July 20]. Available from: <https://www.afro.who.int/news/obesity-rising-africa-who-analysis-finds>.
2. Kluger, J. More than half of the world will be obese by 2035, report says. 2023. [Accessed on 2024, July 20]. Available from: <https://time.com/6264865/global-obesity-rates-increasing/>.
3. World Health Organization. Obesity and overweight. 2024 [Accessed on 2024, July 21]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/obesity-and-overweight>.
4. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Adult obesity facts. 2017. [Accessed on 2024, July 20]. Available from: https://www.cdc.gov/obesity/adult-obesity-facts/?CDC_AAref_Val=https://www.cdc.gov/obesity/data/adult.html.
5. World Health Organization. Obesity. 2021. [Accessed on 2024, July 22]. Available at: <https://www.who.int/news-room/facts-in-pictures/detail/6-facts-on-obesity>.
6. Ali, M.M., Parveen, S., Williams, V., Dons, R., Uwaifo, G.I. Cardiometabolic comorbidities and complications of obesity and chronic kidney disease (CKD). *J Clin Transl Endocrinol* 2024;36:100341.
7. World Obesity. World obesity atlas. 2023. [Accessed on 2024, July 20]. Available from: https://www.worldobesityday.org/assets/downloads/World_Obesity_Atlas_2023_Report.pdf.
8. Chukwuonye, I.I., Ohagwu, K.A., Ogah, O.S., John, C., Oviasu, E., Anyabolu, E.N., et al. Prevalence of overweight and obesity in Nigeria: systematic review and meta-analysis of population-based studies. *PLOS Global Public Health* 2022;2(6):e0000515.

9. Ellecom, J.B., Shaw, I., Adams, G.G. Obesity in Nigerian Adults and the Associated Cause and Impact on the Population. *J Diabet Res Rev Report* 2022;4(4):1-11.
10. Chung, W., Lim, S. Factors contributing to educational differences in obesity among women: Evidence from South Korea. *BMC Public Health* 2020;20(1):1136.
11. Ng, M., Fleming, T., Robinson, M., Thomson, B., Graetz, N., Margono, C., et al. Global, regional, and national prevalence of overweight and obesity in children and adults during 1980–2013: a systematic analysis for the global burden of disease study 2013. *The Lancet* 2014;384(9945):766-81.
12. Dinsa, G.D., Goryakin, Y., Fumagalli, E., Suhrcke, M. Obesity and socioeconomic status in developing countries: a systematic review. *Obesity Rev* 2012;13(11):1067-79.
13. World Health Organization. Non-communicable Diseases: mortality. 2021. [Accessed on 2024, July 21]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/data/gho/data/themes/topics/topic-details/GHO/ncd-mortality>.
14. Population Reference Bureau. For women in the U.S., obesity links to socioeconomic status and poor diet. 2010 [Accessed on 2024, July 21]. Available from: <https://www.prb.org/resources/for-women-in-the-u-s-obesity-links-to-socioeconomic-status-and-poor-diet/>.
15. Chaddha, A., Jackson, E.A., Richardson, C.R., Franklin, B.A. Technology to help promote physical activity. *Am J Cardiol* 2017;119(1):149-152.
16. Ma, T., Bennett, T., Lee, C.D., Wicklow, M. The diurnal pattern of moderate-to-vigorous physical activity and obesity: a cross-sectional analysis. *Obesity* 2023;31(10):2638-47.
17. Ogden, C.L. Prevalence of obesity among adults, by household income and education—United States, 2011–2014. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep* 2017;66(50):1369-1373.
18. Ayogu, R.N.B., Ezeh, M.G., Udentia, E.A. Epidemiological characteristics of different patterns of obesity among adults in rural communities of south-east Nigeria: a population-based cross-sectional study. *BMC Nutrition* 2022;8(1):59.
19. Ritchie, H., Roser, M. Obesity. *Our World Data*. 2024 Jan. [Accessed on 2024, July 21]. Available from: <https://ourworldindata.org/obesity>.
20. World Obesity. Global Obesity Observatory. 2019. [Accessed on 2024, July 21]. Available from: https://data.worldobesity.org/country/nigeria-158/#data_overview.
21. Uduu, O. 7 major factors driving obesity in Nigeria. 2023. [Accessed on 2024, July 7]. Available from: <https://dataphyte.com/latest-reports/7-major-factors-driving-obesity-in-nigeria/>.
22. Barber, C., Rankin, J., Heslehurst, N. Maternal body mass index and access to antenatal care: a retrospective analysis of 619,502 births in England. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth* 2017;17:290.
23. Dow, M.L., Szymanski, L.M. Effects of overweight and obesity in pregnancy on health of the offspring. *Endocrinol Metabol Clinic* 2020;49(2):251-63.
24. Lane-Cordova, A.D., Khan, S.S., Grobman, W.A., Greenland, P., Shah, S.J. Long-term cardiovascular risks associated with adverse pregnancy outcomes: JACC review topic of the week. *J Am College Cardiol* 2019 ;73(16):2106-16.
25. Driscoll, A.K., Gregory, E.C. Increases in pre-pregnancy obesity: United States, 2016-2019. *NCHS data brief* 2020;1(392):1-8.
26. Cameron, N.A., Molsberry, R., Pierce, J.B., Perak, A.M., Grobman, W.A., Allen, N.B., et al. Pre-pregnancy hypertension among women in rural and urban areas of the United States. *J Am College Cardiol* 2020;76(22):2611-9.
27. Virani, S.S., Alonso, A., Aparicio, H.J., Benjamin, E.J., Bittencourt, M.S., Callaway, C.W., et al. Heart Disease and Stroke Statistics—2021 Update: A Report from the American Heart Association. *Circulation* 2021;143(8):e254-e743.
28. Sole, K.B., Staff, A.C., Laine, K. Maternal diseases and risk of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy across gestational age groups. *Pregnancy Hypertens* 2021;25:25-33.
29. Ghimire, P.R., Akombi-Inyang, B.J., Tannous, C., Agho, K.E. Association between obesity and miscarriage among women of reproductive age in Nepal. *PLoS One* 2020;15(8):e0236435.
30. Akselsson, A., Rossen, J., Storck-Lindholm, E., Rådestad, I. Prolonged pregnancy and stillbirth among women with overweight or obesity—a population-based study in Sweden including 64,632 women. *BMC Pregnancy Childbirth* 2023;23(1):21.
31. Akpan, U.B., Akpanika, C., Okpebri, K.O., Udeke, U., Etuk, S.J. The Prevalence of Maternal Obesity at First Antenatal Visit and Pregnancy Outcomes: A Prospective Cohort Study in a Southern Nigerian Region. *Niger J Med* 2023;32(5):495-500.
32. Kim, J., Ayabe, A. Obesity in Pregnancy. *InStatPearls*. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing, 2024. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK572113/>.
33. Rodriguez, B.S., Vadakekut, E.S., Mahdy, H. Gestational diabetes. *InStatPearls*. 2024. StatPearls Publishing. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/31424780/>.
34. Li, S., Zhu, Y., Yeung, E., Chavarro, J.E., Yuan, C., Field, A.E., et al. Offspring risk of obesity in childhood, adolescence and adulthood in relation to gestational diabetes mellitus: a sex-specific association. *Int J Epidemiol* 2017;46(5):1533-41.

35. Meek, C.L. An unwelcome inheritance: childhood obesity after diabetes in pregnancy. *Diabetologia* 2023 ;66(11):1961-70.
36. Senbanjo, O.C., Akinlusi, F.M., Ottun, T.A. Early pregnancy body mass index, gestational weight gain and perinatal outcome in an obstetric population in Lagos, Nigeria. *Pan Afr Med J* 2021;39:136.
37. Ezeanochie, M.C., Ande, A.B., Olagbuji, B.N. Maternal obesity in early pregnancy and subsequent pregnancy outcome in a Nigerian population. *Afr J Reproductive Health* 2011;15(4):55-9.
38. Sanchez, E., Burns, A.C., Parker, L. Local government actions to prevent childhood obesity. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press. 2010. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/25032346/>.
39. Billingsley, H.E., Carbone, S., Lavie, C.J. Dietary fats and chronic non-communicable diseases. *Nutrients* 2018;10(10):1385.
40. Bandura, A. Social cognitive theory: An agentic perspective. *Ann Rev Psychol* 2001;52(1):1-26.
41. Mackenzie, T., Sallis, J., Beets, M., Beighle, A., Erwin, H., Lee, S. Physical education's role in public health: steps forward and backward over 20 years and hope for the future. *Res Q Exerc Sport* 2012;83:125-35.
42. World Health Organization. Global Recommendations on Physical Activity for Health; WHO Press: Geneva, Switzerland, 2010. Available from: <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789241599979>.
43. Schafer, M.H., Ferraro, K.F. The stigma of obesity: does perceived weight discrimination affect identity and physical health?. *Soc Psychol Quarter* 2011;74(1):76-97.
44. Cuypers, K., Kvaløy, K., Bratberg, G., Midthjell, K., Holmen, J., Holmen, T.L. Being normal weight but feeling overweight in adolescence may affect weight development into young adulthood—an 11-year followup: the HUNT study, Norway. *J Obesity* 2012;2012(1):601872.
45. Espeland, M.A., Glick, H.A., Bertoni, A., Brancati, F.L., Bray, G.A., Clark, J.M., et al. Impact of an intensive lifestyle intervention on use and cost of medical services among overweight and obese adults with type 2 diabetes: the action for health in diabetes. *Diab Care* 2014;37(9):2548-56.
46. Lehnert, T., Sonntag, D., Konnopka, A., Riedel-Heller, S., König, H.H. The long-term cost-effectiveness of obesity prevention interventions: systematic literature review. *Obesity Rev* 2012;13(6):537-53.
47. Greaves, C.J., Sheppard, K.E., Abraham, C., Hardeman, W., Roden, M., Evans, P.H., et al. Systematic review of reviews of intervention components associated with increased effectiveness in dietary and physical activity interventions. *BMC Public Health*. 2011;11:119.
48. Hawkes, A.L., Chambers, S.K., Pakenham, K.I., Patrao, T.A., Baade, P.D., Lynch, B.M., et al. Effects of a telephone-delivered multiple health behavior change intervention (CanChange) on health and behavioral outcomes in survivors of colorectal cancer: a randomized controlled trial. *J Clin Oncol* 2013;31(18):2313-21.
49. Whittemore, R., Jeon, S., Grey, M. An internet obesity prevention program for adolescents. *J Adolescent Health* 2013;52(4):439-47.
50. Rogers, V.W., Hart, P.H., Motyka, E., Rines, E.N, Vine, J., Deatrick, D.A. Impact of let's go! 5-2-10: a community-based, multisetting childhood obesity prevention program. *J Pediatr Psychol* 2013;38(9):1010-20.
51. Kumanyika, S.K., Whitt-Glover, M.C., Haire-Joshu, D. What works for obesity prevention and treatment in black Americans? Research directions. *Obesity Rev* 2014;15:204-12.
52. Adams, A.K., Scott, J.R., Prince, R., Williamson, A. Using community advisory boards to reduce environmental barriers to health in American Indian Communities, Wisconsin, 2007–2012. *Preventing Chronic Disease* 2014;11(9):E160 .
53. Napolitano, M.A., Hayes, S., Bennett, G.G., Ives, A.K., Foster, G.D. Using Facebook and text messaging to deliver a weight loss program to college students. *Obesity* 2013;21(1):25-31.
54. Inman, D.D., van Bakergem, K.M., LaRosa, A.C., Garr, D.R. Evidence-based health promotion programs for schools and communities. *Am J Prev Med* 2011;40(2):207-19.
55. Schuette, S.A., Cordero, E., Slosburg, K., Addington, E.L., Victorson, D. A scoping review of positive lifestyle and wellness interventions to inform the development of a comprehensive health promotion program: "HealthPro". *Am J Lifestyle Med* 2019;13(4):336-46.
56. Brown, O., Quick, V., Colby, S., Greene, G., Horacek, T.M., Hoerr, S., et al. Recruitment lessons learned from a tailored web-based health intervention Project YEAH (Young Adults Eating and Active for Health). *Health Education* 2015;115(5):470-9.
57. Akarolo-Anthony, S.N., Willett, W.C., Spiegelman, D., Adebamowo, C.A. Obesity epidemic has emerged among Nigerians. *BMC Public Health* 2014;14:1-9.
58. Greenlee, H.A., Crew, K.D., Mata, J.M., McKinley, P.S., Rundle, A.G., Zhang, W., et al. A pilot randomized controlled trial of a commercial diet and exercise weight loss program in minority breast cancer survivors. *Obesity* 2013;21(1):65-76.